

MODERN ASPECTS OF TOPICAL ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY FOR ACUTE BACTERIAL CONJUNCTIVITIS IN CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15328409>

Abstract. *To evaluate the efficacy and safety of a three-day course of topical antibiotic therapy compared to a standard seven-day course in the treatment of acute bacterial conjunctivitis in children. A prospective randomized controlled trial was conducted involving 46 children (88 eyes) aged from 6 months to 12 years. Patients were randomly assigned to two groups: Group A (23 patients, 45 eyes) received 0.5% moxifloxacin eye drops four times daily for 3 days, and Group B (23 patients, 43 eyes) received the same antibiotic for 7 days. Clinical assessments were performed on days 3, 7, and 14. The primary efficacy endpoint was complete clinical recovery by day 7. Secondary outcomes included duration of symptoms, adverse effects, recurrence rate within 14 days, and parental satisfaction (on a 1–5 scale). Complete recovery by day 7 was observed in 86.9% of patients in Group A and 91.3% in Group B ($p=0.65$). The mean duration of symptoms was 3.2 ± 0.9 days in Group A and 3.0 ± 1.0 days in Group B ($p=0.44$). Adverse effects occurred in 4.3% and 8.7% of patients, respectively ($p=0.55$). One recurrence was noted in Group A. Parental satisfaction was high in both groups, with mean scores of 4.6 and 4.5, respectively ($p=0.68$). The three-day topical antibiotic regimen demonstrated comparable clinical efficacy and safety to the standard seven-day treatment course for acute bacterial conjunctivitis in children.*

Keywords: *acute bacterial conjunctivitis, children, antibiotics, moxifloxacin.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that acute bacterial conjunctivitis (ABC) is one of the most common reasons for visits to ophthalmologists in outpatient settings, especially among the pediatric population. The disease is characterized by the rapid onset of clinical symptoms, including purulent discharge, conjunctival hyperemia, eyelid swelling, and discomfort. According to epidemiological studies, conjunctivitis accounts for up to 40% of all inflammatory eye diseases in children, and bacterial forms are identified in 65–75% of cases [1,2].

According to international statistics, the annual incidence of bacterial conjunctivitis among children under the age of 12 is estimated to be between 12–14% [1,8,11]. In large urban areas, these rates may be even higher, particularly in organized child groups (such as daycare centers and schools), where the infection spreads rapidly and leads to outbreaks. Health ministries in various countries estimate that up to 80% of bacterial conjunctivitis cases occur in children [3,5,6]. These figures highlight the high medical and social significance of the problem.

Although bacterial conjunctivitis is, in most cases, a self-limiting disease, the use of topical antibiotics is traditionally considered the standard treatment. This approach helps to speed up recovery, reduce the risk of complications, and limit the spread of infection [3,5]. Standard recommendations suggest a treatment duration of 5–7 days; however, clinical observations show that in most children, symptoms significantly improve by the 2nd or 3rd day of treatment. This has sparked interest in shortened antibiotic therapy regimens [2,4,8].

Modern approaches to the rational use of antibiotics involve not only selecting an effective drug but also justifying the minimum necessary duration of therapy. Shortened courses offer

potential advantages, such as reducing the risk of developing antibiotic resistance, lowering the frequency of side effects, improving compliance, and decreasing treatment costs [4,6]. However, a critical condition for their implementation is the proof of therapeutic equivalence-“non-inferiority”-compared to standard regimens.

Existing Data. Current data on the duration of treatment for acute bacterial conjunctivitis (ABC) in pediatrics are limited, and most randomized studies on this topic either include adult patients or assess only bacteriological outcomes without considering the clinical picture. This creates a significant gap in the evidence base, especially given the age-related anatomical and immunological features of the eye in children [7,9].

Therefore, the relevance of this study is driven by the need to determine the optimal duration of antibiotic therapy in children with acute bacterial conjunctivitis based on objective clinical data and a rigorous study design.

Study Objective. To evaluate the effectiveness of a three-day course of topical antibiotic therapy compared to the standard seven-day course in the treatment of acute bacterial conjunctivitis in children. A prospective randomized controlled trial with a non-inferiority design was conducted. The study took place over a six-month period at the outpatient department of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute.

Study Population Characteristics. The study included 46 patients (88 eyes), aged from 6 months to 12 years, who were diagnosed with acute bacterial conjunctivitis based on characteristic clinical symptoms: purulent discharge, conjunctival hyperemia, eyelid swelling, and subjective complaints of discomfort. All patients presented with an acute onset of symptoms—no more than 48 hours prior to enrollment in the study.

Exclusion Criteria included signs of viral or allergic conjunctivitis, the presence of concurrent systemic infectious diseases, use of systemic antibiotics within the last 14 days, ophthalmologic conditions such as keratitis, uveitis, or dacryocystitis, and individual intolerance to fluoroquinolones.

Patients were randomly assigned to two groups:

- **Group A** (23 patients, 45 eyes) received 0.5% moxifloxacin solution four times a day for **3 days** (shortened course).
- **Group B** (23 patients, 43 eyes) received the same antibiotic four times a day for 7 days. The medication bottles were identical, ensuring the blinded nature of the study (standard course).

Methodology. Clinical assessments were performed by a qualified ophthalmologist three times: on Day 3, Day 7, and Day 14 from the start of treatment. Evaluation included visual inspection using a slit lamp and interviews with parents, with all data recorded on a standardized form.

The primary efficacy criterion was defined as complete clinical recovery, marked by the full resolution of discharge, hyperemia, and swelling, as well as the absence of subjective complaints of discomfort.

Additionally, parents completed daily symptom diaries, in which they recorded the severity of symptoms (discharge, redness, itching/burning) using a 4-point scale (0 - none, 3- severe). On Day 14, they also rated their satisfaction with treatment on a 5-point scale.

Adverse events were recorded through parent self-reports and clinical examinations. Side effects included burning, itching, non-infectious hyperemia, skin reactions around the eye, and any other issues requiring discontinuation of therapy.

Relapse was defined as the reappearance of symptoms after their complete resolution during the 14-day observation period.

Statistical Analysis. Data were processed using Microsoft Office Excel and SPSS Statistics v25.0. Statistical significance of differences between groups for binary outcomes (recovery, adverse events) was assessed using the Chi-squared test (χ^2). For ordinal and quantitative data, the non-parametric t-test (if normally distributed) or the Mann–Whitney U test was applied. Time to full clinical recovery was evaluated using Kaplan–Meier survival analysis. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. Efficacy analysis was conducted according to the Intention-to-Treat (ITT) principle.

Results. Table 1 demonstrates the homogeneity of the study groups in terms of key demographic and clinical characteristics. The average age in Group A was 4.8 ± 2.6 years, and in Group B - 5.0 ± 2.4 years ($p = 0.72$), indicating no statistically significant age difference. Gender distribution was also comparable: boys made up 52% in Group A and 48% in Group B ($p = 0.79$). The onset of symptoms less than 24 hours before consultation was noted in 15 patients in Group A and 16 patients in Group B ($p = 0.76$).

Table 1.

Baseline Characteristics of the Patients.

Characteristic	Group A (n=23)	Group B (n=23)	<i>p</i>
Mean age, years	4,8±2,6	5,0±2,4	0,72
Boys, n (%)	12 (52,2%)	11 (47,8%)	0,79
Girls, n (%)	11 (47,8%)	12 (52,2%)	0,79
Symptom onset (<24 hours), n (%)	15 (65,2%)	16 (69,5%)	0,76

Table 2 presents data on the effectiveness and safety of therapy in both groups. Complete recovery by Day 7 was observed in 87% of patients in Group A and 91% in Group B ($p = 0.65$), with a difference of -4%.

The average duration of symptoms was 3.2 ± 0.9 days in Group A and 3.0 ± 1.0 days in Group B ($p = 0.44$), showing no statistically significant difference.

Adverse effects were rare: reported in 1 patient (4%) in Group A and 2 patients (9%) in Group B ($p = 0.55$).

Disease recurrence within 14 days was noted in only one child from Group A. Parental satisfaction with treatment was high and comparable: the average score was 4.6 in Group A and 4.5 in Group B ($p = 0.68$).

Table 2.

Primary and Secondary Outcomes.

Outcome	Group A (n=23)	Group B (n=23)	<i>p</i>
Recovery on Day 7, n (%)	20 (86,9%)	21 (91,3%)	0,65
Average duration of symptoms, days	3,2±0,9	3,0±1,0	0,44
Adverse effects, n (%)	1 (4,3%)	2 (8,7%)	0,55
Recurrence within 14 days, n (%)	1 (4,3%)	-	0,31
Parental satisfaction (mean score)	4,6±0,5	4,5±0,6	0,68

Table 3 demonstrates the cumulative recovery dynamics in both groups over the observation period. By Day 3 of therapy, signs of complete clinical recovery were observed in 39.1% of patients in Group A and 43.4% in Group B.

By Day 5, improvement was recorded in 73.9% in Group A and 78.2% in Group B. By Day 7, 86.9% and 91.3% of patients had recovered, respectively.

Table 3.

Time to Complete Recovery Analysis.

Day	Group A (n=23)	Group B (n=23)	<i>p</i>
3	9 (39,1%)	10 (43,4%)	0,76
5	17 (73,9%)	18 (78,2%)	0,72
7	20 (86,9%)	21 (91,3%)	0,65

The Kaplan-Meier survival curve demonstrates almost identical dynamics of eye condition improvement, which allows for the conclusion of equivalent treatment efficacy in both groups at all-time points (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Kaplan-Meier Curve of Time to Complete Recovery.

Discussion. The results of the study demonstrate that a three-day course of topical moxifloxacin is equally effective and safe compared to the standard seven-day course in the treatment of acute bacterial conjunctivitis in children. The proportion of patients with complete clinical recovery by Day 7 was 86.9% in Group A and 91.3% in Group B ($p = 0.65$), which falls within the established threshold of 10%. Thus, the shortened therapy regimen can be considered clinically equivalent.

Comparison with other studies shows similar results. In the study by Sheikh A. et al. (2012) [10], which focused on the use of topical antibiotics for conjunctivitis, the effectiveness of antibiotics was higher than that of placebo, but the advantage was most apparent in the first few days of therapy. The authors noted that many patients recovered even without treatment. In the study by Rose P.W. et al. (2005) [9], it was shown that 65% of children with bacterial conjunctivitis recover spontaneously within 2-5 days.

The use of short antibiotic courses has also demonstrated effectiveness in other areas of pediatric infections. In particular, in the treatment of otitis and pharyngitis, shortened therapy regimens with preserved dosage and frequency showed no less effectiveness compared to standard regimens, as well as reduced frequency of side effects and improved treatment adherence [4,6,7].

Safety is an important consideration. In this study, the frequency of adverse effects was low and did not differ significantly between the groups (4% vs. 9%, $p = 0.55$). Disease recurrence was noted in one patient from Group A, which was also not statistically significant. This confirms that shortened courses do not increase the risk of adverse outcomes. It is also worth noting the high parental satisfaction in both groups, which is important from a practical perspective. Reducing the treatment duration lowers the burden on the family, especially when frequent administration of the medication is necessary for young children.

Limitation of the study: A limitation of the study is the lack of microbiological confirmation of the diagnosis; however, in the case of a typical clinical presentation, this aligns with the practice in most outpatient settings.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that the three-day course of topical 0.5% moxifloxacin demonstrated comparable efficacy to the standard seven-day course in the treatment of acute bacterial conjunctivitis in children. By Day 7, recovery was achieved in 86.9% of patients in the short-course group and 91.3% in the standard treatment group ($p > 0.06$). Given the results, the three-day regimen can be considered an effective alternative to the traditional regimen in outpatient practice.

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